

Extension of a dG- P_N Neutron Transport Solver to 3D Polyhedral Meshes

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ABSTRACT

Accurate neutron transport simulation in complex reactor geometries is becoming increasingly important with the emergence of advanced reactor concepts and accidental configurations that may break the usual Axial 2D-extruded symmetry. This work presents the ongoing extension of the NYMO neutron transport solver to fully three-dimensional meshes. The solver relies on the spherical harmonics (P_N) method for the angular approximation, coupled with the discontinuous Galerkin (dG) method for the spatial discretization of the Boltzmann transport equation. Previous developments of the NYMO solver focused on 2D meshes and were later extended to 2D-extruded configurations. Therefore, the present paper describes the numerical methods developed to generalize the scheme to fully 3D polyhedral meshes, including non-convex cells, through the computation of elementary matrices based on the exact integration of monomials over polyhedra cells. It also introduces a new approach for evaluating hemispherical integrals of real spherical harmonics using Wigner rotation matrices, a technique widely used in quantum mechanics and now adapted to neutron transport. These methods have been implemented in the NYMO solver of the APOLLO3[®] neutronic code, and first studies demonstrate the accuracy of the 3D numerical scheme for cells with planar faces. Further developments are ongoing to extend the approach to meshes with cylindrical-arc faces. However, the generation of fully arbitrary polyhedral meshes remains a challenging task, particularly when dealing with non-convex regions due to the difficulty of efficiently determining consistent outward normal directions for all faces.

Keywords: P_N method; discontinuous Galerkin method; Polyhedral meshes; Integration over polyhedra; Hemispherical integrals.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, most neutronics solvers are limited to 1D, 2D, 2D-extruded, or 3D tetrahedral meshes, which are sufficient for modeling conventional reactors such as pressurized water reactors (PWRs). However, the emergence of more advanced reactor concepts, including Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) and Generation IV systems, makes numerical simulations increasingly challenging owing to the growing geometric complexity. Moreover, in some accidental or off-normal conditions, reactors that are well represented by a 2D-extruded geometry under normal operation, such as sodium-cooled fast reactors (SFRs), may lose their regular geometric configuration due to mechanical and thermal deformations.

For these specific configurations, a neutronic solver capable of handling arbitrary 3D meshes is therefore highly relevant. To address this need, the present work focuses on extending the NYMO neutron transport solver to full 3D meshes. The NYMO solver relies on the P_N method for angular discretization, similar to the approach implemented in the SCEPTRE radiation transport code [1]. This angular treatment is coupled with a discontinuous Galerkin (dG) method for the discretization of the transport equation. It is integrated into the APOLLO3[®] [2] code system as both a lattice and core solver. In its current form, NYMO can already handle 2D [3], and 2D-extruded [4] configurations on unstructured

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and non-conformal meshes, including regions with planar and curved faces. This work is part of an ongoing first year PhD thesis at CEA-SERMA that extends the solver to three-dimensional polyhedral meshes. The first stage concerns arbitrary polyhedra with planar faces, while future developments will address curved-face regions. The main objective of this paper is to introduce the numerical methods required for the accurate computation of the elementary matrices, which become particularly challenging in 3D configurations [5, 6].

1. NUMERICAL MODELING OF THE STATIONARY TRANSPORT EQUATION

Before presenting the newly developed numerical methods, this section briefly introduces the discontinuous Galerkin method coupled with the P_N approximation (dG- P_N), implemented in the NYMO solver. The numerical scheme, which can also be applied to fully 3D meshes, is described in detail in [3]. For simplicity and without loss of generality, we consider here the stationary, one group transport equation in a fissile medium. The phase space is defined as $X = D \times \mathbb{S}^2$, where D denotes the spatial domain of an arbitrary mesh cell and \mathbb{S}^2 the unit sphere. Thus, the transport equation can then be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \omega \cdot \nabla u(x, \omega) + \Sigma_t(x) u(x, \omega) &= \frac{1}{k_{\text{eff}}} Fu(x, \omega) + Hu(x, \omega) && \text{in } X, \\ u(x, \omega) &= f(x, \omega) && \text{on } \Gamma^-, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

with $\Gamma^- = \{(x, \omega) \in \partial D \times \mathbb{S}^2 \mid \omega \cdot \mathbf{n}(x) < 0\}$, where ∂D is the boundary of D and $\mathbf{n}(x)$ represents the outward unit normal vector at point $x \in \partial D$. Moreover, $u(x, \omega)$ denoting the angular flux, F and H the fission and scattering operators, respectively, $\Sigma_t(x) u(x, \omega)$ the absorption term and, $f(x, \omega)$ is the incoming flux from upwind cells or the boundary condition. Following a variational approach, the transport equation (1) is multiplied by $v + \frac{1}{\Sigma_t} \omega \cdot \nabla v$, where v is an arbitrary function in the test space W , and then integrated over X . After several algebraic manipulations, the formulation for the discontinuous Galerkin case reads as follows:

$$\text{Find } u \in W \text{ such that } \forall v \in W, \quad a(u, v) = h(u, v) + \frac{1}{k_{\text{eff}}} p(u, v) + L(v), \quad (2)$$

where $a, h, p : W \times W \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are bilinear forms and $L : W \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a linear form. These forms are detailed in [3].

Angular flux approximation. The P_N method consists of expanding the angular flux $u(x, \omega)$ in the real spherical harmonic basis $(y_\ell^k)_{0 \leq \ell \leq N, -\ell \leq k \leq \ell}$:

$$u(x, \omega) \approx \sum_{\ell=0}^N \sum_{k=-\ell}^{\ell} u_\ell^k(x) y_\ell^k(\omega) \quad (x, \omega) \in D \times \mathbb{S}^2. \quad (3)$$

The coefficients u_ℓ^k represent the angular flux moments associated with the spherical harmonics y_ℓ^k . For each spatial region D , these moments are further expanded over a local polynomial basis $(\varphi_j)_{1 \leq j \leq J}$, leading to the following space-angle approximation:

$$u(x, \omega) \approx \sum_{j, \ell, k} u_{\ell j}^k \varphi_j(x) y_\ell^k(\omega), \quad (x, \omega) \in D \times \mathbb{S}^2. \quad (4)$$

By the same way, the source terms and the incoming flux $f(x, \omega)$ are also expanded over the same space-angle basis $(\varphi_j(x) y_\ell^k(\omega))_{1 \leq j \leq J, 0 \leq \ell \leq N, -\ell \leq k \leq \ell}$.

For each cell D , the transport equation is solved in the test space W , spanned by the basis functions

$\{\varphi_j(x) y_\ell^k(\omega)\}$. By inserting the test functions $v = \varphi_i(x) y_n^m(\omega)$ and the expansion of u given by (4) into the formulation (2), one obtains, for each tuple $(1 \leq i \leq J, 0 \leq n \leq N, -n \leq m \leq n)$, the following discrete problem:

$$\sum_{j,\ell,k} u_{\ell j}^k a(\varphi_j y_\ell^k, \varphi_i y_n^m) = \sum_{j,\ell,k} u_{\ell j}^k h(\varphi_j y_\ell^k, \varphi_i y_n^m) + \frac{1}{k_{\text{eff}}} \sum_{j,\ell,k} u_{\ell j}^k p(\varphi_j y_\ell^k, \varphi_i y_n^m) + L(\varphi_i y_n^m). \quad (5)$$

After several algebraic manipulations detailed in [3] and denoting $\mathbf{u} = (u_{\ell j}^k)_{\ell k j}$, the discrete weak form yields the following matrix system, assuming the one-group approximation:

$$A \mathbf{u} = Q. \quad (6)$$

The detailed expressions of all the elementary matrices introduced above are given in [3]. The development of the matrices A and the source term Q leads to a linear combination of the following elementary contributions:

$$\begin{aligned} A^0(i, n, m, j, \ell, k) &= \sum_{p=1}^3 \sum_{q=1}^3 \left(\int_D \partial_p \varphi_i \partial_q \varphi_j \, d\mathbf{r} \right) \left(\int_{S^2} \omega_p \omega_q y_n^m y_\ell^k \, d\omega \right), \\ A^1(i, n, m, j, \ell, k) &= \delta_{n,\ell} \delta_{m,k} \int_D \varphi_i \varphi_j \, d\mathbf{r}, \\ A^2(i, n, m, j, \ell, k) &= \sum_{p=1}^3 \left(\int_D (\partial_p \varphi_i) \varphi_j \, d\mathbf{r} \right) \left(\int_{S^2} \omega_p y_n^m y_\ell^k \, d\omega \right), \\ A^+(i, n, m, j, \ell, k) &= \sum_{\mathcal{F} \in \partial D} \int_{\mathcal{F}} \varphi_i \varphi_j \left(\int_{\{\omega \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{F}} > 0\}} y_n^m y_\ell^k \langle \omega \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{F}} \rangle \, d\omega \right) \, ds, \\ A_{\mathcal{F}}^-(i, n, m, j, \ell, k) &= \int_{\mathcal{F}} \varphi_i \varphi_j \left(\int_{\{\omega \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{F}} < 0\}} y_n^m y_\ell^k \langle \omega \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{F}} \rangle \, d\omega \right) \, ds. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Here, $\omega = (\omega_p)_{1 \leq p \leq 3}$ denotes the direction vector in the Cartesian space \mathbb{R}^3 , and $\mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{F}}$ is the unit outward normal to the local face $\mathcal{F} \in \partial D$. The computation of these elementary matrices is well established for the 2D cases [3], as well as for 2D-extruded meshes [4]. However, the task becomes significantly more challenging in full 3D meshes. Indeed, $\mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{F}}$ can take any direction on the unit sphere S^2 , which makes the integration over the half-sphere non-trivial for the matrices $A_{\mathcal{F}}^-$ and A^+ . Moreover, the computational mesh may be unstructured, thus each cell D can differ in both size and shape, and may include complex or non-planar faces. The following two sections provide a brief overview of the computation of the spatial and angular integrals. For more details, the reader is referred to [5, 6].

2. SPATIAL INTEGRATION OVER A POLYHEDRA

The first task is to develop a numerical method to compute the integral of monomial functions over an arbitrary polyhedra. Indeed, since the functions $(\varphi_j)_{1 \leq j \leq J}$ form the local polynomial basis, the integration over the polyhedra D of a product of basis functions or their derivatives (7) can be reduced to the computation of integrals of monomial functions of the form:

$$I(i, j, k) = \int_D x^i y^j z^k \, dx \, dy \, dz, \quad (i, j, k) \in \mathbb{N}^3. \quad (8)$$

Since D is an arbitrary polyhedra, classical quadrature methods were avoided because of their implementation complexity and potentially prohibitive computational cost. Moreover, a linear mapping to

a reference element is only possible for simplex meshes. A possible strategy would be to decompose D into tetrahedra. However, designing a generalized and robust algorithm for arbitrary polyhedral decompositions is far from trivial and could work for planar faces polyhedron only.

In contrast, the literature describes a method known as the Lasserre method (LM) [7], which allows to calculate integrals of monomials over polytopes in an exact and recursive way. This approach is robust and evaluates the integral (8) near machine-precision accuracy, although a naïve recursive implementation may become expensive for high polynomial degrees. Moreover, despite the newly developed computational method, it is not certain that the Lasserre integration method remains relevant for regions with cylindrical-arc faces. This is why a new method, based on the dimension reduction of integrals through divergence and Stokes' theorems, has been developed. It allows one to transform the integration over the volume D into a linear combination of edge integrations [5].

2.1. Divergence/Stokes reduction to faces and edges

This method consists of two main steps. First, a polynomial vector field $F(x, y, z)$ is constructed such that $\nabla \cdot F = x^i y^j z^k$. Applying the divergence theorem then reduces the volume integral to a sum of surface integrals over the faces:

$$\int_D x^i y^j z^k \, dx \, dy \, dz = \int_D \nabla \cdot \mathbf{F}(x, y, z) \, dx \, dy \, dz = \sum_{\mathcal{F} \in \partial D} \int_{\mathcal{F}} \mathbf{F} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{F}} \, ds. \quad (9)$$

Next, for each face \mathcal{F} of ∂D , a new vector field \mathbf{G} is built satisfying $\nabla \times \mathbf{G} = \mathbf{F}$. Applying Stokes' theorem, each face integral is reduced to a sum of line integrals along the edges e of the face \mathcal{F} :

$$\sum_{\mathcal{F} \in \partial D} \int_{\mathcal{F}} \mathbf{F} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{F}} \, ds = \sum_{\mathcal{F} \in \partial D} \int_{\mathcal{F}} (\nabla \times \mathbf{G}) \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{F}} \, ds = \sum_{\mathcal{F} \in \partial D} \sum_{e \in \partial \mathcal{F}} \int_e \mathbf{G} \cdot d\boldsymbol{\ell}. \quad (10)$$

Remark: The orientation of the outward normal vectors $\mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{F}}$ for all faces must be known consistently. For convex regions, determining the direction of the outward face vector is straightforward, which is not obvious when dealing with non-convex meshes. Therefore, we rely on mesh generator to provide this information. The meshing process can be performed with the *SALOME* platform [8], developed at CEA, which supports hexahedral and tetrahedral meshes.

3. INTEGRALS OF PRODUCTS OF REAL SPHERICAL HARMONICS OVER HEMISPHERES

Another sensitive case concerns the computation of the elementary matrices $A_{\mathcal{F}}^-$ and A^+ , especially the evaluation of the following integral:

$$I_{nm\ell k}^{\pm} = \int_{\omega \in \mathbb{S}_{\mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{F}}}^{\pm}} y_n^m(\omega) y_{\ell}^k(\omega) \langle \mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{F}}, \omega \rangle \, d\omega, \quad (11)$$

where $\mathbb{S}_{\mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{F}}}^{\pm} = \{\omega \in \mathbb{S}^2 \mid \pm \mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{F}} \cdot \omega > 0\}$, and $\mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{F}}$ denotes the outward normal vector at point $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{F}$.

For the 2D and 2D-extruded cases, [3] demonstrated that the integrand can be separated into two functions f and g such that

$$I_{nm\ell k}^{\pm} = \int_{\omega(\theta, \varphi) \in \mathbb{S}_{\mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{F}}}^{\pm}} f(\theta) g(\varphi) \, d\theta \, d\varphi.$$

These functions can then be expanded into trigonometric series and integrated analytically. However, in the fully 3D case when the normal vector $\mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{F}}$ is not necessarily aligned with the vertical or horizontal direction, the integration bounds for the variables θ and φ remain coupled.

Figure 1. The hemisphere $S_{n_{\mathcal{F}}}^+$ in the reference frame \mathcal{R} oriented along the normal vector $\mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{F}}$.

Figure 2. The hemisphere $S_z^+ = R^T S_{n_{\mathcal{F}}}^+$ in the rotated frame \mathcal{R}' obtained after applying the frame rotation R^T .

Thus, a change of variables is required to reduce the general 3D case to the standard configuration where the normal $\mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{F}}$ is aligned with the z -axis \mathbf{k} , thereby allowing the separation of variables.

To express the integral in the reference frame where the normal is aligned with the z -axis, we introduce the rotation operator $R(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ defined by its associated Euler angles (α, β, γ) in Z-Y-Z convention. With appropriately chosen angles, the rotation maps the local frame \mathcal{R}' , associated with the standard orientation \mathbf{k} , to the global frame \mathcal{R} oriented along the face normal $\mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{F}}$, such that

$$\omega = R(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) \omega' \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{F}} = R(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) \mathbf{k}. \quad (12)$$

To perform this change of coordinates, one can take advantage of the rotation invariance properties of spherical harmonics.

Rotation Invariance Properties. In quantum mechanics, this property is well known [9] for complex spherical harmonics Y_n^m :

$$Y_n^m(R \omega') = \sum_{p=-n}^n D_{pm}^{(n)}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) Y_n^p(\omega'), \quad (13)$$

where $D_{pm}^{(n)}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ are the elements of the Wigner D -matrix corresponding to the rotation $R(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$. In the literature, this property has been less extensively investigated for real spherical harmonics. The article [6] addresses this gap by deriving the rotation invariance relation for real spherical harmonics, using $(\Delta^{(n)})_{pm}$ to denote the Wigner matrices in the real basis:

$$y_n^m(R \omega') = \sum_{p=-n}^n \Delta_{pm}^{(n)}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) y_n^p(\omega'), \quad (14)$$

For polyhedra cells with planar faces, the outward normal vector is constant over each face. Consequently, the Euler angles and the rotation operator remain constant throughout the face integration. In this case, by substituting (14) into the main integral (11) and applying the rotation relation (12), we

obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_{nm\ell k}^{\pm} &= \sum_{p=-n}^n \sum_{q=-\ell}^{\ell} \Delta_{pm}^{(n)}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) \Delta_{qk}^{(\ell)}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) \int_{\omega' \in S_k^{\pm}} y_n^p(\omega') y_{\ell}^q(\omega') \langle \mathbf{k}, \omega' \rangle d\omega' \\
 &= \sum_{p=-n}^n \sum_{q=-\ell}^{\ell} \Delta_{pm}^{(n)}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) \Delta_{qk}^{(\ell)}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) I_{np\ell q}^{\pm \mathbf{k}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

For $I_{np\ell q}^{\pm \mathbf{k}}$ corresponding to the 2D-extruded case (horizontal face), the variable separation (3) can be applied to the integrand, and the resulting integral can then be evaluated using the method described in [3].

Remark: For meshes including cylindrical-arc faces, a similar approach can be applied by rotating the local reference frame into a cylindrical coordinate system. This allows the angular and spatial integrals to be evaluated consistently with the curved meshes.

4. APPLICATION

With these methods at hand, all elementary matrices can now be constructed for a full 3D mesh case. The local equation (6) is solved for each cell within an iterative process.

To assess the accuracy of the methods developed in the previous sections, several Cartesian 2D-extruded meshes were considered. In such configurations, the multiplication factor k_{eff} computed with the 3D implementation should match the value obtained with the reference 2D-extruded formulation. For the following study, a subset of models with Cartesian geometry was extracted from the Takeda benchmark [10]. We focus here on the first configuration: a small light-water reactor (LWR) model with two energy groups and reflective boundary conditions on the coordinate planes, taking advantage of the eightfold symmetry of the cuboid. Two cases were analyzed: (i) control rods fully withdrawn, and (ii) control rods inserted. For both configurations, k_{eff} values computed with the 2D-extruded and 3D implementations were compared for P_N orders ranging from 1 to 6, using a local polynomial basis of degree 1 (dG₁). The corresponding results are summarized in Table I, where the relative errors in pcm between the computed k_{eff} and the reference values are presented. For each configuration, the reactor domain is discretized using identical cells of size $1 \times 1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^3$ cells for both the 2D-extruded and fully 3D cases.

Table I. Deviation of k_{eff} from the Monte Carlo reference (in pcm) for the 2D-extruded and 3D implementations for both control rod configurations.

(i) Control rods withdrawn (reference $k_{\text{eff}} = 0.9780$).

mesh	P ₁	P ₃	P ₅	P ₂	P ₄	P ₆
2D-extr.	-3141	-272	-123	+452	+55	-9
3D	-3141	-272	-123	+452	+55	-9

(ii) Control rods inserted (reference $k_{\text{eff}} = 0.9624$).

mesh	P ₁	P ₃	P ₅	P ₂	P ₄	P ₆
2D-extr.	-2483	-85	-12	+356	+25	+1
3D	-2483	-85	-12	+356	+25	+1

For all tested cases, no difference in k_{eff} is observed between the 2D-extruded and 3D solvers. In both implementations, the coefficients of the elementary matrices agree close to machine precision, which

Figure 3. Examples of motif-cell refinement patterns used in the validation tests.

demonstrates the correctness and consistency of the 3D formulation. It should be noted that elementary matrices for each cell are computed only once prior to the iterative flux solution. Since this pre-computation time is negligible, execution times for 2D extruded and 3D geometries are nearly identical. NYMO's performance in Cartesian geometry was benchmarked against the IDT MOC solver [11]. While the IDT S_8 configuration yields a reactivity error of -56 pcm in 16 s, NYMO achieves an error of 55 pcm in 12 s using P_4 order, and -9 pcm in 36 s using P_6 order.

In a second series of tests, each region of the previous Cartesian meshes was further subdivided into two subregions, as illustrated in Fig. 3. The objective of this study is to assess the robustness of the method when applied to meshes containing non-convex or irregular cells, and to verify that the computed k_{eff} remains nearly unchanged when Cartesian regions are subdivided. The results are summarized in Table II, which presents the relative errors in pcm between the computed k_{eff} and the reference values.

Table II. Deviation of k_{eff} from the Monte Carlo reference (in pcm) for different mesh refinement patterns in the withdrawn and inserted control-rod cases (dG_1 parameter).

(i) Withdrawn control rods (reference $k_{\text{eff}} = 0.9780$).

Cell refinement	P_1	P_3	P_5	P_2	P_4	P_6
(a)	-3141	-272	-123	+452	+55	-9
(b)	-3319	-298	-136	+501	+62	-6
(c)	-3322	-295	-136	+489	+59	-9

(ii) Inserted control rods (reference $k_{\text{eff}} = 0.9624$).

Cell refinement	P_1	P_3	P_5	P_2	P_4	P_6
(a)	-2483	-85	-12	+356	+25	+1
(b)	-2582	-86	-13	+368	+27	0
(c)	-2581	-85	-14	+364	+25	0

For identical input data and parameters, all computed k_{eff} values remain nearly identical, as expected, confirming the robustness of the proposed approach. At P_6 order, transitioning from mesh (a) to (b) doubles the number of cells and degrees of freedom while reducing mesh regularity. This results in an increase in computation time from 36 s to 189 s. However, moving from pattern (b) to (c) yields minor changes in execution time and the number of outer iterations, demonstrating that the 3D scheme

effectively supports meshes with non-convex cells.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

The implementation of new numerical techniques for the construction of elementary matrices in the $dG-P_N$ framework has demonstrated the robustness and relevance of this approach for handling polyhedral meshes. The method appears particularly well suited for the simulation of complex reactor configurations and accidental scenarios. However, additional verification and validation tests are required to further assess the method's accuracy. A dedicated effort must also be devoted to mesh generation, as each face must be associated with a correctly oriented outward normal vector. This task becomes particularly challenging for meshes containing non-convex regions.

The developments presented here have been applied only to regions with planar faces. Nevertheless, the approach can naturally be extended to meshes including cylindrical-arc faces. This extension allows the method to be applied to both lattice and core calculations.

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